

ORIGINAL ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

eDNA and Citizen Science Reveal Hidden Fish Biodiversity in Climate-Stressed Urban Ports of the Mediterranean Sea

Bénédicte Madon¹ | Rachel Haderlé² | Emma Arotcharen³ | Romain David⁴ | Quentin Fontaine⁵ | Michel Marengo⁶ | Hélène Thomas⁷ | Antonio Torralba⁸ | Alice Valentini⁹ | Jean-Luc Jung¹⁰

¹Escuela Superior de Ingenieros/AICIA, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain | ²Institut de Systématique, Évolution, Biodiversité (ISYEB), Station Marine de Dinard du Muséum National D'histoire Naturelle, Dinard, France | ³Université de Franche-Comté, SUP-FC Batiment Bachelier, Besançon, France | ⁴European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA), Bruxelles, Belgium | ⁵Station Marine STARESO, Calvi, France | ⁶STation de REcherches Sous-Marines et Océanographiques (STARESO), Calvi, France | ⁷La Rochelle Université, Littoral, Environnement et Sociétés (LIENSs), UMR 7266 CNRS—La Rochelle University, La Rochelle, France | ⁸Escuela Superior de Ingenieros, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain | ⁹SPYGEN, Savoie Technolac—Bât. Koala, France | ¹⁰ISYEB, Station Marine de Dinard du Muséum National D'histoire Naturelle, Dinard, France

Correspondence: Antonio Torralba (torralba@us.es)

Received: 25 January 2025 | **Revised:** 30 May 2025 | **Accepted:** 3 June 2025

Funding: This work was supported by DANUBIUS-IP, 101079778. SAFARI, 101147432, EMFF QUAMPO, PFEA800219DM0940001.

Keywords: biodiversity | citizen science | DNA | environmental | environmental monitoring | extreme weather | metabarcoding

ABSTRACT

This paper provides a pioneering study case on monitoring fish biodiversity in ports through the eDNA and citizen science approach. eDNA samples were collected in the spring and in fall 2022 in the ports of Calvi, L'Île-Rousse, STARESO, Saint-Florent. Samples collected led to the identification of 73 taxa. These ports appeared to harbor at least 20% of the known teleost biodiversity in Corsica and 11% of the Mediterranean teleost biodiversity. The ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse displayed the highest taxonomic, phylogenetic, and functional diversities and appeared the most similar. However, taxonomic turnover highlighted that none of the 4 ports was a subset of any of the others. In August 2022, an extreme climate event (ECE) struck Corsica, offering a unique opportunity to collect data under abnormal conditions. Although it is not possible to distinguish the seasonal effect from the ECE effect in the fall, we detected in all ports but Saint-Florent an increase in taxonomic richness, phylogenetic, and functional diversity: we did not only detect new species but also showed that these species led to an increase in the local representativeness of phylogenetic diversity, most likely correlated with new functional traits. The port of Saint-Florent displayed the highest relative phylogenetic diversity, that is, a smaller but evolutionarily more distinct group of species. Our study demonstrated the robustness and relevance of eDNA citizen science coupled with relevant indicators for port biodiversity monitoring and emphasized the need for more research and targeted conservation efforts to better understand and mitigate the ecological impacts of ports while exploring their potential as habitats.

1 | Introduction

In the dynamic and ecologically sensitive environments of ports, effective biodiversity monitoring is critical for understanding the anthropic impacts and preserving aquatic ecosystems amidst increasing anthropogenic pressures. Ports and marinas and surrounding areas are particularly unique as they represent the

outmost of urban areas, being critical intersections characterized by intense industrial, commercial, and recreational usage contributing to high levels of anthropogenic stress through vessel traffic impact, habitat modification, and water pollution (Madon et al. 2022). Yet, recent studies seemed to suggest unexpected biodiversity in seaports, with species richness similar to that of nearby marine protected area ones (Manel et al. 2024). This

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Environmental DNA* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

challenges traditional assumptions about biodiversity hotspots and highlights the need for comprehensive monitoring of these urban marine environments, as little is known about their biodiversity (Madon et al. 2023). These hubs of maritime activity, while essential for economic and recreational purposes, can present challenges for traditional biodiversity assessment methods, such as direct sampling, trapping, or visual surveys (Madon et al. 2023). These approaches can be invasive, disruptive, and logistically complex, especially in the busy and variable conditions typical of these areas. In this context, the development of environmental DNA (eDNA) has been revolutionary, offering a non-invasive and highly efficient alternative for monitoring biodiversity (Baird and Hajibabaei 2012; Valentini et al. 2009). By analyzing the DNA extracted from environmental samples such as soil, air, or water, also called eDNA, this provides a comprehensive snapshot of species presence and distribution without the need for physical capture or direct observation (e.g., Charvoz et al. 2021; Haderlé et al. 2024). Importantly, this method allows researchers to potentially detect any known species, from microorganisms to larger marine animals, drawing up lists of key biodiversity inventories. While most marine biodiversity monitoring and conservation efforts focus on protected areas, the first attempts at evaluating this biodiversity revealed rather surprising results: ports and nearby reserves showed similar levels of α -diversity (Manel et al. 2024).

The combination of eDNA with citizen science further enhances its effectiveness (Cohn 2008; Knudsen et al. 2023; Kvalheim et al. 2024; Sandahl and Tøttrup 2020; Zhang et al. 2024). The citizen science approach extends the capability of biodiversity monitoring programs by enabling more extensive, long-term data collection across diverse locations and times otherwise impractical for research institutions alone (Coché et al. 2021; de Sherbinin et al. 2021; Lehtiniemi et al. 2020; Luzar et al. 2011). This collaborative effort not only enhances biodiversity assessments but also fosters greater public awareness and involvement in conservation efforts, especially in urban ecosystems (Couvet et al. 2008).

By leveraging both eDNA-based approaches and citizen science, ports and marinas can gain a deeper understanding of their aquatic environments, drive effective management strategies, and promote sustainable practices that benefit both local ecosystems and broader conservation goals. Key to understanding biodiversity patterns in ports and informing port management is the choice of relevant metrics. In urban ecosystems such as ports, the development of appropriate biodiversity indicators is essential for port management to evaluate the effectiveness of different conservation approaches and encourage good practices, for example, through the AFNOR certification “Port active in biodiversity” according to the criteria of the standard ISO 18725 “Clean Harbors” (Source: ISO 18725:2024), or the environmental program CÂYOLI of the Guadeloupe Caribbean Port.

With this paper, we aim at providing a pioneering study case based on a joint effort between biologists and citizens for monitoring biodiversity through the eDNA and metabarcoding approaches in ports. eDNA samples were collected to establish a baseline of species presence and distribution in four Corsican ports. This initial set of data from spring 2022 aimed to offer a baseline of the ecosystem health and diversity under normal

conditions. However, after this sampling campaign, a derecho struck Corsica on the 18th of August 2022 (Pucik 2022). This extreme climate event (ECE) offered a unique opportunity to collect data under abnormal conditions, and eDNA samples were collected again, at the same sites and following the same protocol in the fall 2022. The two batches of eDNA samples were similarly analyzed with a metabarcoding approach, allowing us to list inventories of marine fish biodiversity in each sampling location in the spring and fall 2022. Although it is not possible at this time to disentangle the seasonal and the ECE effects in the fall and to conduct formal statistical analysis, we gained valuable insights into biodiversity changes, and we proposed an innovative set of indicators to provide a first baseline of biodiversity patterns in Corsican ports using eDNA and citizen science. This study illustrates the potential of the combined use of eDNA, metabarcoding, and citizen science in capturing temporal biodiversity variations in urban marine environments and highlights the need for conservation strategies, including ongoing monitoring to better understand ecosystem resilience in the face of climate-related disturbances and improved disaster preparedness for similar future events.

2 | Material and Methods

2.1 | Study Area

The eDNA study took place in 4 ports in Corsica: Calvi (coordinates (WGS 84): 42.56726, 8.76163), L'Île-Rousse (coordinates (WGS 84): 42.64151, 8.93639), Saint-Florent (coordinates (WGS 84): 42.67993, 9.30031), STARESO (coordinates (WGS 84): 42.58044, 8.72542) (Figure 1). These ports were all characterized by varying anthropogenic pressures coming from port activities as well as differences in sediment and hydrological conditions (Appendix 1). The port of Calvi is a medium-size marina (capacity of 376 recreational boats) with sandy bottom and non-turbid water. The port of L'Île-Rousse hosts a small marina (capacity of 286 recreational boats) with similar sediment and hydrological conditions as the port of Calvi and serves as a ferry terminal with daily ferry arrivals and departures. The port of Saint-Florent is the largest recreational port (capacity of 930 recreational boats), located at a river mouth with a muddy bottom and turbid water. STARESO is a marine station located at a cape at the edge of a rocky drop-off. During the derecho on the 18th of August 2022, winds reached 197 km/h in Calvi and 206 km/h in L'Île-Rousse, breaking wind-speed records in both locations.

2.2 | eDNA Sampling

A total of 25 samples were collected: in the spring (June 2022), 12 samples (2 in Calvi and STARESO, 5 in L'Île Rousse, 3 in Saint Florent) and in the fall (October 2022), 13 samples (3 in STARESO, Calvi and Saint-Florent and 4 in L'Île-Rousse). Samples were taken at several sites within each port to cover all types of port environmental conditions to reduce intra-port variability: these locations included the marina, the port entrance, and when present, the careening station, the fishing dock, and the gas station. Within each port, the same sites were sampled at the 2 sampling occasions: the “post-storm” sampling took place 2 months after the ECE due to administrative constraints and

FIGURE 1 | Geographical distribution of the sampled ports from the project QUAMPO in Corsica, France: Ports of Calvi, L'Île-Rousse, Saint-Florent, and STARESO and taxonomic richness obtained from the eDNA study before and after the storm in 2022.

ended up coinciding with the fall. All samples were collected using the citizen science kit of SpyGen. All details and information are available in the metadata of the fully-open data in GBIF: <https://www.gbif-uat.org/dataset/542de543-5e19-4d6d-835b-8531b7d90a26>.

The field survey methodology was modified from Biggs et al. (2015). The sampling kit was composed of a sterile water sampling ladle, a self-supporting sterile Whirl-Pak bag, a sterile syringe, gloves to minimize contamination, a 0.22- μM eDNA dual filter capsule (Sylphium molecular ecology, Groningen, Netherlands) and 7.5 mL of CL1 preservation buffer (SPYGEN, Le Bourget-du-Lac, France). Samples of 100 mL of water were collected with the ladle between 1 m below the sea surface, totalling 2 L per site. Collectors did not enter the water to avoid possible contamination. Water samples were homogenized by gently shaking the Whirl-Pak bag and then filtered through the capsule. The preservation buffer was added to the capsule, which was preserved at room temperature before the eDNA extraction.

2.3 | Citizen Science

In our study, we define citizen as anyone but the 2 principal investigators (PIs) who had previous experience in eDNA sampling. Therefore, we considered students and postdoctoral researchers with no prior experience in eDNA sampling as "citizen." While this group may generally be more methodical or scientifically trained, we also encountered young participants—particularly children passionate about fishing—who demonstrated remarkable knowledge of local species and showed great care and skill during sampling, highlighting the difficulty of defining the term "citizen" (Bonney et al. 2009;

Haklay et al. 2021). Since citizens are not able, for logistical and safety reasons, to do a sea transect within ports as traditionally done by scientists (e.g., Haderlé et al. 2024; Manel et al. 2024; Kenworthy et al. 2018), all samples were collected from port pottons. Various citizen categories were involved in the sampling and collected more than half of the samples in this study (13 out of the 25 samples). In the spring sampling, we involved school children in the port of L'Île-Rousse (3 samples, including 1 failure), and students and postdocs in all ports which represented 5 samples of the spring samples. After the storm hit Corsica in August 2022, the 2 PIs sampled the ports of L'Île-Rousse and Saint-Florent (7 samples) and a postdoc the port of Calvi and STARESO (6 samples), again using the same locations in October 2022.

2.4 | eDNA Laboratory Analysis

DNA extraction was performed at SPYGEN (Le Bourget du Lac, SPYGEN) in a dedicated room for water DNA sample extraction, equipped with positive air pressure, ultraviolet treatment, and frequent air renewal, using NucleoSpin Soil (Macherey-Nagel GmbH & Co., Düren, Germany), starting from step 4, and following the manufacturer's instructions. The elution was performed by adding 100 μL of SE buffer twice. After the DNA extraction the samples were tested for inhibition by quantitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) (Biggs et al. 2015). If the sample was considered inhibited, it was diluted fivefold before the amplification. DNA amplifications were performed in a final volume of 25 μL using teeo primers following the protocol described in Valentini et al. (2016). Twelve replicate PCRs were run per filtration and primers were 5'-labeled with an eight-nucleotide tag unique to each PCR replicate, with identical tags in forward and reverse. The purified PCR products were

pooled into equal volumes to achieve a theoretical sequencing depth of 100,000 reads per sample (Appendix 2). Two libraries (one for each marker) were prepared by DNAGensee (Le Bourget du Lac, France) using the TruSeq PCR-Free kit (Illumina) and sequenced them separately. Paired-end sequencing were carried out using a NextSeq 1000 sequencer (2×150 bp, Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) and the NextSeq 1000/2000 P1 Reagents kit (v3; Illumina), following the manufacturer's instructions. Negative extraction controls and negative PCR controls (ultrapure water, one for each marker) were amplified (12 replicates) and sequenced in parallel to the samples to monitor possible contaminations.

The sequences obtained were analyzed using the programs implemented in the OBITools toolkit (Boyer et al. 2016) based on a previous protocol (Valentini et al. 2016). After the sequencing, forward and reverse reads were assembled and then demultiplexed for primer pair and tags. Sequences shorter than 20 bp or occurring less than 10 times per sample were discarded. Amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) were identified and matched with the reference database for Mediterranean fish species (Dalongeville et al. 2022) as well as with the reference database of the DNA sequences retrieved from the release 247 of GenBank to obtain the taxonomic assignation for each ASV. Considering the occasional misassignment of a few sequences to the wrong sample due to tag-jumps (Schnell et al. 2015), all sequences with a frequency of occurrence below 0.001 per taxon and per library were removed as well. Index-Hopping (MacConaill et al. 2018) was also corrected with a threshold empirically determined per sequencing batch using experimental blanks (i.e., combinations of tags do not present in the libraries), for a given sequencing batch across libraries (Polanco Fernández et al. 2021).

2.5 | Data Analysis

2.5.1 | Species Community Composition

Regarding the occurrences, the assignment at the species level was not possible for several ASV ($n=10$). We considered these ASV as corresponding to distinct species, based on the postulate that these ASV sequences were not assignable to a species and were different enough from the nearest identified species, in general of the same genus or family.

We pooled the eDNA samples into 8 bulk samples, each bulk sample corresponding to a port (Calvi, STARESO, L'Île Rousse and Saint Florent) and a sampling occasion (spring vs. post-storm). We studied fish species composition using the Jaccard index which provided insights into both species richness and community compositions differences between all dyads of bulk samples. The beta-diversity components of the ports were analyzed using the R package "adespatial" (Dray et al. 2012). A Jaccard dissimilarity index was computed for all bulk sample dyads using the following formula: $J = (b + c) / (a + b + c)$, where a was the sum of the number of species detected in the two bulk samples 1 and 2, b was the number of species detected in the bulk sample 1 minus a , and c was the number of species in bulk sample 2 minus a (Dray et al. 2012). The more similar two bulk samples are in terms of list of species detected, the more J tends

toward $J=0$, and $J=1$ for two totally different bulk samples. The dissimilarity indices were calculated to produce a dissimilarity matrix of species compositional changes among all dyads of bulk samples. We further calculated the proportion of dissimilarity explained by: 1- species replacement (or taxonomic turnover) which relates to the absence of a taxon in one of the two bulk samples of ports (i.e., port bulk samples per sampling occasion), where it has been replaced by another species (itself absent in the other bulk sample) (Baselga 2012); 2- nestedness, referring to the difference in taxonomic richness between bulk samples, when the bulk sample with the lowest number of species tend to be a subset of another one (Baselga 2012).

2.5.2 | Biodiversity Indicators

We computed a collection of biodiversity indicators from the presence-absence matrix of detections, chosen to empower the analysis of differences in taxonomic composition between ports, and before and after the storm in all four ports:

- Taxonomic richness (R) corresponded to the number of different taxa identified.
- Phylogenetic diversity (PD) corresponded to Faith's (Faith 1992) phylogenetic diversity value (total sum of tree branch lengths) and was computed using the package "rtrees" (Li 2023) and "picante" (Kembel et al. 2010). While taxonomic richness provides a snapshot of species numbers, PD gives a deeper understanding of how those species contribute to the overall evolutionary diversity of an ecosystem. High PD is often associated with more resilient and stable ecosystems, as it suggests greater functional diversity;
- Functional diversity (FD) corresponds to the number of unique functional groups for each port (Dalongeville et al. 2022). Functional diversity was obtained by taking into account several characteristics of the taxa detected ("CommonLength," "Weight," "LongevityWild," "AnaCat," "MigratRef," "DepthRangeShallow" and "DepthRangeDeep" from the "rfishbase" package (Boettiger et al. 2012)), calculating the "Gower distance" (Gower and Warrens 2017) and grouping the taxa by "PcoA" (Mouillot et al. 2021) into functional entities. Based on the functional group values determined for each taxon, we run a principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) using the "factoextra" package in order to investigate the patterns of these groups in relation to ports and sampling occasions (Kassambara and Mundt 2017);
- "Invasive" corresponded to the number of invasive species detected in each sample, the "invasive" character was taken from Openrefine and Wikidata (invasive to—P5588) (Pal and Mukhopadhyay 2022);
- The vulnerability indicator ("Vulner") corresponds to the average of the fishing vulnerability values provided for each fish species by Fishbase (Dalongeville et al. 2022);
- The "RedList" indicator (Dalongeville et al. 2022) corresponds to the weighted sum of the IUCN statuses of the species detected ($VU=1$, $EN=2$, $CR=3$). The IUCN statuses of the species were obtained using Openrefine and

Wikidata (IUCN conservation status—P141) (Pal and Mukhopadhyay 2022);

- Mean trophic level (“TLmean”) corresponded to an analysis of the trophic community structure, deduced from the trophic level (TL) of all species present in the community. TL, determined by predator–prey interactions, expresses the position of an organism within a food web. The lowest trophic level values ($TL=1$) are assigned to the primary producers at the base of the food web, with herbivorous in the subsequent level ($TL=2$) and the highest values ($TL \geq 4$) are assigned to predators at the top. To study fish community trophic structure and potential shifts in community composition in terms of trophic level after the storm, fish were classified in three trophic categories following the TL of each species from Fishbase (Froese and Pauly 2010): (1) carnivore: $TL > 2.8$, (2) herbivore: $2 < TL < 2.19$, and (3) omnivore: $2.2 < TL < 2.79$. Finally, we used an adaptation of the mean trophic level (MTL) as it is currently impossible to make inference about biomass with eDNA data. We computed the mean TL (TL_{mean}) as the mean of the TL of all species present in each bulk sample.

3 | Results

We identified a total of 73 taxa (72 teleost taxa, 1 elasmobranch taxa) over our 8 bulk samples: 63 at the species level, 9 at the genus level, and 1 at the family level, in 4 ports using the citizen science kit and 2 sampling occasions (Table 1, Figure 1).

Of these 73 species, 70 were identified in the fall against 56 in the spring. Hence, 17 species were gained after the storm and 3 species were lost: *Thunnus thynnus*, *Lophius budegassa*, and *Gobius* sp. Finally, the invasive species *Lepomis gibbosus* (sun perch) was detected in October in the port of Saint-Florent. Further surveys are needed to confirm this observation, which seems plausible given the peculiarity of the port of Saint-Florent located at the mouth of 2 local rivers (the Poghju and the Alisu). Finally, our results yielded the taxonomic richness as in Dalongeville et al. (2022) in the Calvi area with 50 species in common between the two studies.

3.1 | Taxonomic Richness (R)

3.1.1 | Spatial Variation

We identified the greatest number of species in the port of L'Île-Rousse (49 species) and Calvi (48 species). STARESO displayed an intermediate number of species (37 species) and Saint-Florent showed the lowest species richness with 29 species over the 2 sampling occasions (Table 1). In terms of similarity, the ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse seemed to be the most similar, uniquely sharing 9 species, while the ports of STARESO and Saint-Florent appeared the most dissimilar, sharing no unique species as a pair (Figure 2). The central overlap of 13 species common to all ports suggested a core set of species that are generalists, well adapted to a variety of conditions across the entire region. The port of Calvi presented the greatest number of unique species (8 species) and the port of Saint-Florent the smallest with only 2 unique species.

In terms of the components explaining the dissimilarity between the ports, the dissimilarity was globally explained for 60% by the taxonomic turnover and for 40% by nestedness. These results highlighted that none of the 4 ports was a subset of any of the others and that the ports mainly differed in their diversity by their taxonomic turnover. In particular, this taxonomic turnover reached its highest value ($TT=0.73$) for the most similar ports (Calvi and L'Île-Rousse) highlighting that, despite being the most similar pair, neither of the ports was a subset of the other (Table 2).

3.1.2 | Temporal Variation: In the Spring Versus in the Fall

All ports but the port of Saint-Florent displayed a sharp increase in their taxonomic richness in the fall, for example, from 28 to 43 species detected in the port of Calvi between the spring and the fall, 27 to 44 in the port of L'Île-Rousse (Figure 3, Appendix 3).

As expected with regards to the Venn diagram (Figure 2), the dissimilarity Jaccard coefficient was the smallest between the ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse ranging from $J=0.51$ in the spring to $J=0.62$ between Calvi_Spring and L'Île-Rousse_PS, and the greatest between the ports of STARESO and Saint-Florent, reaching $J=0.8$ in the spring (Figure 4).

For each port, the dissimilarity between the spring and in the fall was equal and was the greatest for the ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse (0.52) while the ports of STARESO and Saint-Florent were slightly less dissimilar between the spring and after the storm (0.46) (Figure 4). In terms of the components of the β -diversity index, taxonomic turnover best explained the dissimilarities between the ports and the sampling occasions being at its maximum after the storm between the ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse ($TT=0.73$) (Table 2).

3.2 | Phylogenetic Diversity (PD)

3.2.1 | Spatial Variation

The ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse presented the highest phylogenetic diversity, that is, the species detected in the port of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse were phylogenetically more diverse, potentially covering a broader range of evolutionary lineages (Appendix 3). On the other hand, the port of Saint-Florent displayed the highest relative PD, meaning that, given its taxonomic richness, species represented longer evolutionary branches than in any other ports: the port of Saint-Florent hosted a smaller, but in some respects, evolutionarily more distinct group of species as compared to the other ports. Finally, the port of STARESO presented the lowest relative PD while having a higher taxonomic richness than the port of Saint-Florent (Appendix 3).

3.2.2 | Temporal Variation: In the Spring Versus in the Fall

Phylogenetic diversity was the highest at the port of L'Île-Rousse ($PD=3022$) and the lowest at the port of Saint-Florent ($PD=1425$)

TABLE 1 | list of the 73 identifications (63 at species-level, 9 at genus-level, 1 at family-level) ordered by family, corresponding number of observations (*n*) in the samples (max. 25) and corresponding ports where identified in June and October 2022 (Port of Calvi:). Species classified VU, EN or CR on the IUCN Red List are highlighted in blue, alien species are highlighted in red.

Species	Order	Family	Genus	<i>n</i>	Spring 2022	Fall 2022
<i>Apogon imberbis</i>	Kurtiformes	Apogonidae	Apogon	6		
<i>Belone belone</i>	Belontiiformes	Belontiidae	Belone	4		
<i>Aidablennius sphynx</i>	Blenniiformes	Blenniidae	Aidablennius	1		
<i>Parablennius sp.</i>	Blenniiformes	Blenniidae	Parablennius	11		
<i>Parablennius</i>	Blenniiformes	Blenniidae	Parablennius	8		
<i>Parablennius incognitus</i>	Blenniiformes	Blenniidae	Parablennius	1		
<i>Parablennius gattorugine</i>	Blenniiformes	Blenniidae	Parablennius	1		
<i>Salaria pavo</i>	Blenniiformes	Blenniidae	Salaria	3		
<i>Bothus podas</i>	Pleuronectiformes	Bothidae	Bothus	1		
<i>Trachurus sp.</i>	Carangiformes	Carangidae	Trachurus	5		
<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i>	Perciformes	Centrarchidae	Lepomis	1		
<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	Clupeiformes	Clupeidae	Sardina	9		
<i>Sardinella aurita</i>	Clupeiformes	Clupeidae	Sardinella	1		
<i>Engraulis sp.</i>	Clupeiformes	Engraulidae	Engraulis	1		
<i>Lepadogaster candollei</i>	Blenniiformes	Gobiesocidae	Lepadogaster	1		
<i>Lepadogaster lepadogaster</i>	Blenniiformes	Gobiesocidae	Lepadogaster	1		
<i>Gobius sp.</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Gobius	1		
<i>Gobius bucchichi</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Gobius	8		
<i>Gobius cobitis</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Gobius	3		
<i>Gobius cruentatus</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Gobius	9		
<i>Gobius niger</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Gobius	14		
<i>Millerigobius macrocephalus</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Millerigobius	3		
<i>Pseudaphya ferreri</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Pseudaphya	3		
<i>Zebrus zebrus</i>	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	Zebrus	2		
<i>Istiophorus albicans</i>	Istiophoriformes	Istiophoridae	Istiophorus	2		
<i>Coris julis</i>	Labriformes	Labridae	Coris	8		
<i>Labrus sp.</i>	Labriformes	Labridae	Labrus	3		
<i>Symphodus sp.</i>	Labriformes	Labridae	Symphodus	7		
<i>Symphodus ocellatus</i>	Labriformes	Labridae	Symphodus	3		
<i>Symphodus tinca</i>	Labriformes	Labridae	Symphodus	13		
<i>Thalassoma pavo</i>	Labriformes	Labridae	Thalassoma	5		
<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	Lophiiformes	Lophiidae	Lophius	2		
<i>Mola mola</i>	Tetraodontiformes	Molidae	Mola	1		
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	Eupercaria	Moronidae	Dicentrarchus	7		
<i>Chelon auratus</i>	Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	Chelon	14		
<i>Chelon labrosus</i>	Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	Chelon	20		
<i>Chelon ramada</i>	Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	Chelon	10		
<i>Liza sp.</i>	Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	Chelon	5		
<i>Mugil sp.</i>	Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	Mugil	5		
<i>Oedalechilus laevis</i>	Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	Oedalechilus	13		
<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	Syngnathiformes	Mullidae	Mullus	4		
<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Syngnathiformes	Mullidae	Mullus	10		
<i>Muraena helena</i>	Anguilliformes	Muraenidae	Muraena	5		
<i>Ceratoscopelus maderensis</i>	Myctophiformes	Myctophidae	Ceratoscopelus	1		
<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Myliobatiformes	Myliobatidae	Mobula	1		
<i>Chromis chromis</i>	Ovalentaria	Pomacentridae	Chromis	14		
<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	Eupercaria	Sciaenidae	Sciaena	3		
<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	Scombriformes	Scombridae	Thunnus	1		
<i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Perciformes	Scorpaenidae	Scorpaena	6		
<i>Scorpaena scrofa</i>	Perciformes	Scorpaenidae	Scorpaena	4		
<i>Serranus cabrilla</i>	Perciformes	Serranidae	Serranus	2		
<i>Serranus hepatus</i>	Perciformes	Serranidae	Serranus	1		
<i>Serranus scriba</i>	Perciformes	Serranidae	Serranus	13		
<i>Boops boops</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Boops	5		
<i>Diplodus annularis</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Diplodus	19		
<i>Diplodus puntazzo</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Diplodus	5		
<i>Diplodus sargus</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Diplodus	21		
<i>Diplodus vulgaris</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Diplodus	14		
<i>Lithognathus mormyrus</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Lithognathus	15		
<i>Oblada melanura</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Oblada	19		
<i>Pagellus acarne</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Pagellus	1		
<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Pagellus	2		
<i>Pagellus erythrinus</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Pagellus	2		
<i>Sarpa salpa</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Sarpa	22		
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Sparus	15		
<i>Spicara sp.</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Spicara	3		
<i>Spondylisoma cantharus</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	Spondylisoma	6		
<i>Sparidae</i>	Spariformes	Sparidae	NA	7		
<i>Sphyraena viridensis</i>	Carangaria	Sphyraenidae	Sphyraena	7		

FIGURE 2 | Venn diagrams showing common and unique numbers of fish species in the 4 Corsican ports: Calvi, L'Île-Rousse, Saint-Florent, STARESO.

TABLE 2 | Proportion of taxonomic turnover (in bold, higher right part of the table) and nestedness (in italic, lower left part of the table) explaining of the Jaccard dissimilarity among ports and sampling occasions (in black when the sampling occasions differed; in green when the sampling occasion was spring; in brown when the sampling occasion was post-storm “PS”; underlined when it was the same port but the sampling occasions differed).

	Calvi_Spring	Calvi_PS	L'Île-Rousse_Spring	L'Île-Rousse_PS	Saint-Florent_Spring	Saint-Florent_PS	STARESO_Spring	STARESO_PS
Calvi_Spring	—	<u>0.59</u>	0.55	0.62	0.53	0.6	0.54	0.55
Calvi_PS	<i>0.41</i>	—	0.61	0.73	0.61	0.69	0.61	0.65
L'Île-Rousse_Spring	<i>0.45</i>	0.39	—	<u>0.63</u>	0.56	0.63	0.57	0.57
L'Île-Rousse_PS	0.38	<i>0.27</i>	<i>0.37</i>	—	0.63	0.71	0.62	0.66
Saint-Florent_Spring	<i>0.47</i>	0.39	<i>0.44</i>	0.37	—	<u>0.62</u>	0.57	0.56
Saint-Florent_PS	0.4	<i>0.31</i>	0.37	<i>0.29</i>	<i>0.38</i>	—	0.65	0.64
STARESO_Spring	<i>0.46</i>	0.39	<i>0.43</i>	0.38	<i>0.43</i>	0.35	—	<u>0.54</u>
STARESO_PS	0.45	<i>0.35</i>	0.43	<i>0.34</i>	0.44	<i>0.36</i>	<i>0.46</i>	—

after the storm which also presented respectively the highest and smallest taxonomic richness (Appendix 3). Again, the port of Saint-Florent was the only port to display a decrease in *PD* in the fall (Figure 3, Appendix 3). However, values of *PD/R*, taking the ratio between *PD* and *R*, the port of Saint-Florent displayed the highest relative *PD* ($PD/R=79$) post-storm while the ports of Calvi and STARESO experienced a decrease in their relative *PD* between the spring and in the fall (Figure 3, Appendix 3). The port of L'Île-Rousse in the spring displayed a rather low relative phylogenetic diversity with regard to its high taxonomic richness (Appendix 3).

3.3 | Functional Diversity (FD)

3.3.1 | Spatial Variation

The port of Calvi had also the highest functional diversity *FD* closely followed by the port of L'Île-Rousse. However, again,

when looking at the ratio *FD/R*, the port of Saint-Florent was the port with the most diverse functional groups relative to its low taxonomic diversity while the port of L'Île-Rousse displayed one of the lowest relative functional diversities relative to its high taxonomic diversity.

3.3.2 | Temporal Variation: In the Spring Versus in the Fall

The ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse had the highest functional diversity at both sampling occasions (Figure 3; Appendix 3). In the port of Saint-Florent, a low functional diversity post-storm was consistent with the loss of species and the loss of phylogenetic diversity. The port of STARESO had the lowest *FD* and *FD/R* along with the lowest taxonomic and phylogenetic diversity in the spring. As mentioned previously, the port of Calvi saw a decrease in its *PD/R* in the fall but an increase in its *FD/R*,

FIGURE 3 | Evolution of the taxonomic richness, the phylogenetic and relative diversities, the functional and relative diversities between spring and fall in the ports of L'Île-Rousse, Calvi, STARESO and Saint-Florent with the min and max values on the x-axis for each indicator.

meaning that species gained after the storm did not represent very long evolutionary branches but represented more diverse functional groups (Figure 3; Appendix 3).

In terms of functional group distribution across ports and sampling occasions, the port of Saint-Florent and STARESO were similar between the 2 occasions while the ports Calvi and L'Île-Rousse were similar in the spring but not in the fall. The port of Saint-Florent was consistent in terms of functional groups, in the *FD/R* ratio while the port of L'Île-Rousse, which gained the most species in the fall, lost in its *FD/R*, being the only port to display a decrease in this ratio between spring and the fall.

Regarding the spatial distribution of the functional groups, the port of Saint-Florent appeared to host 4 specific functional

groups and was clearly apart from the other ports, both in the spring and in the fall (Figure 5). The port of STARESO was also characterized by 4 functional groups in the spring and in the fall. The remaining functional groups spanned across the ports of L'Île-Rousse and Calvi, with more functional groups present in the fall as compared to the spring.

3.4 | Trophic Level (*TLmean*)

3.4.1 | Spatial Variation

The port of L'Île-Rousse presented the highest *TLmean* and the port of Saint-Florent the lowest (although nothing was significant), reflecting that species hosted in the port of

FIGURE 4 | Jaccard dissimilarity matrix between ports and sampling occasions. Higher values reflect strong differences between species compositions of the compared samples; lower values reflect more similarities between samples.

FIGURE 5 | PCA plot of the 2 first dimensions displaying fish functional group patterns across ports and sampling occasions. The functional group values are those computed for the *FD* indicator, based on ecological traits (e.g., trophic level, mobility, habitat). Analysis performed using the “factoextra” package (Kassambara and Mundt 2017).

Saint-Florent were more primary consumers than in the port of L’Île-Rousse (Appendix 1). For example, in the port of L’Île-Rousse, species with a high trophic level, such as *Zeus faber* (TL=4.5) and *Scorpaena scrofa* (TL=4.3), were detected. In contrast, these species were not found in the port of Saint-Florent, where the community was mostly composed of species with lower trophic levels, corresponding to primary consumers (Table 1). Higher trophic levels are often indicative of healthier ecosystems with a balanced food web, where top predators maintain ecological functions. In our study, all

ports were characterized by fish communities dominated by carnivore species (Figure 6).

3.4.2 | Temporal Variation: In the Spring Versus in the Fall

The port of L’Île-rousse displayed the highest *TLmean* in the spring but the port of Calvi surpassed it in October (Figure 6). The slight increase in *TLmean* between spring and in October

FIGURE 6 | Fish trophic composition as relative number of carnivore, herbivore, and omnivore species and TL_{mean} (sd) in the ports of Calvi, L'Île Rousse, Saint-Florent, and STARESO in the spring and in the fall.

in the ports of Calvi and L'Île Rousse may reflect seasonal recruitment of lower trophic level species (juveniles, primary consumers) in the spring and indicated the dominance of predatory species in the fall. On the contrary, the ports of Saint-Florent and STARESO displayed a lower trophic level in October (although not significant) with an increase in the proportion of respectively, herbivorous and omnivorous (Figure 6). The ports of L'Île Rousse and Calvi exhibited relatively higher and more consistent TL_{means} , indicating a robust trophic structure with a stable presence of top predators (e.g., *Uranoscopus scaber* [$TL = 4.4$]; *Belone belone* [$TL = 4.2$]; *Sparus aurata* [$TL = 3.7$]).

Except STARESO where omnivore species presence increased after the storm to represent 16%, the other ports displayed the same ratios before and after the storm ("carnivore" the most important category representing between 80% and 89% of the total number of species, "omnivore" representing between 9% and 15%, "herbivore" representing less than 7%) (Figure 6). Regarding herbivores, these results appeared rather high given that herbivorous fish species tend to represent around 0.7% of fish species at the Corsican latitude according to Fishbase (Froese and Pauly 2010).

3.5 | Vulner—Invasive—Red List

Vulnerability scores, derived from Fishbase, were relatively consistent across locations, with values ranging from 34 to 43. Higher values, like those in Saint Florent in the fall ($Vulner = 43$), may indicate that the species present were more susceptible to environmental disturbances (Appendix 3).

In terms of invasive species, the invasive sun perch, *Lepomis gibbosus*, was detected in the port of Saint-Florent in the fall.

Finally, the Red List species indicator had a 0 value in all ports in the spring and a post-storm value of 2 in the port of Calvi

where the endangered *Mobula mobular* was detected and of 1 in the port of STARESO where the vulnerable sunfish, *Mola mola*, were detected.

4 | Discussion

Ports are urbanized areas subjected to heavy anthropogenic pressures, including pollution, habitat modification, and vessel traffic, and little is known about the biodiversity they host nor their role in the coastal ecosystem. This knowledge gap is especially critical as port areas may be uniquely vulnerable to compounding climate and anthropogenic pressures (Putnam et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2024). While urbanization often leads to habitat degradation and biodiversity loss, certain urban areas may exhibit high species richness due to novel habitats, for example, artificial structures, that can support diverse fish assemblages (Clynick 2008; Zhang et al. 2024). Our findings highlighted that the relationship between urbanization and fish biodiversity is complex and context-dependent and that conservation strategies should consider the unique characteristics of each urban environment to effectively preserve and enhance fish biodiversity. Our aim was to apply an eDNA-based approach to study fish biodiversity in four Corsican ports, aiming to evaluate the method's effectiveness in the context of seaports. We conducted two seawater sampling campaigns using a protocol tailored for subsequent eDNA extraction and analysis via metabarcoding. Overall, we identified 73 different taxa, representing approximately 20% of the known teleost fish biodiversity in the region. Species inventories varied greatly among the four ports, with Jaccard dissimilarity coefficient ranging from 0.51 to 0.8. Within individual ports, comparisons between spring and fall samples also showed substantial variation, which may reflect seasonal changes as well as the impact of a major climatic event that occurred between the two campaigns. We emphasized key contrasts among ports—particularly the surprising profile of Saint-Florent, which showed high functional and phylogenetic

distinctiveness despite low species richness—and pointed out that such patterns could not have been detected using raw indicators alone. Phylogenetic diversity analysis revealed that taxonomic richness did not always align with phylogenetic diversity. Notably, the port of Saint Florent differed from the other three ports: despite its low taxonomic diversity, it exhibited relatively high phylogenetic diversity, which even increased from spring to autumn—contrary to the trends observed in the other ports.

4.1 | Pitfalls of Using Citizen Science and eDNA

4.1.1 | Heterogeneous Sampling Effort

The use of citizen science certainly has pitfalls, one of which is maintaining the robustness of the experimental design and sampling consistency. While our initial goal was to achieve a consistent number of replicates across all ports (with a targeted number of $n=3$ samples per port), the actual sampling effort was not entirely uniform due to a combination of logistical constraints, unforeseen circumstances, and the inherent uncertainty of working with citizen during sampling activities. This led to limited variations in the number of samples collected between ports in the spring. The most striking difference occurred during the spring sampling campaign, particularly at the port of L'Île-Rousse, where five samples were collected. Of these five, two were obtained through the participation of local school children, which was an important engagement activity but introduced variability and uncertainty in the data generated. In contrast, the neighboring ports of Calvi and STARESO yielded in the spring, only two samples each, primarily due to logistical constraints. These discrepancies highlight the challenges of ensuring homogeneity in citizen science-based projects, particularly when involving educational outreach activities (Fraisl et al. 2022).

Recognizing the potential impact of these differences, we made efforts to reduce this heterogeneity during the fall—after the storm sampling campaign. During this second sampling occasion, we ensured that each port had a consistent number of samples, reaching the targeted number of three per port. This adjustment aimed to bring more balance to the dataset and minimize disparities in sampling effort between locations.

Despite the initial heterogeneity in sampling effort, the results across all ports were remarkably consistent, revealing clear and comparable patterns across both seasons. This coherence in the data suggests that the ecological trends we observed were robust and not significantly influenced by variations in the number of replicates. Furthermore, to address these discrepancies and ensure fair comparisons, we used relative indicators in our analyses. These methodological adjustments helped mitigate the effects of unequal sampling efforts and allowed us to make meaningful comparisons across ports and between sampling occasions.

4.1.2 | Bias in Detection

The species list used in our study was carefully curated with input from local ecological knowledge to ensure relevance and

accuracy and to ensure that taxa identified in this study were ecologically plausible in ports. However, an important caveat to consider when interpreting eDNA-based biodiversity data in port environments is the potential detection of species not residing within the port area but introduced through human activities, particularly fishing (Aglieri et al. 2023). All surveyed ports but STARESO host small-scale artisanal fishing, and while none are major commercial fishing hubs, the movement of fishing vessels in and out of the port may contribute exogenous DNA from species caught offshore or in adjacent habitats (Aglieri et al. 2023). This could result in the detection of taxa that are not actually present within the port itself, potentially inflating estimates of species richness or affecting compositional similarity metrics such as the Jaccard index. In the four ports studied, fisheries are predominantly small-scale, artisanal, and polyvalent. The fishing fleet is primarily composed of small coastal boats known as *petits métiers côtiers* (typically under 9 m in length). These vessels are likely to return with both commercial and non-commercial species, increasing the chance of detecting a wide taxonomic range. The consistent patterns observed across multiple biodiversity indicators further support the robustness of our results. Although detections of highly mobile or commercially targeted species should always be interpreted with care, we emphasize that species filtering should always be applied with caution, and generalized databases should not be used in isolation without considering local contexts. Relying solely on generalized databases (e.g., FishBase) may lead to inappropriate exclusions, and local knowledge should always be consulted before removing species from analyses. We also suggest that future studies incorporate contextual data—such as local fishing records, species habitat preferences, or trophic mobility assessments—to help distinguish resident biodiversity from transient or introduced signals before applying filters. This consideration is particularly important for biodiversity monitoring in urban marine systems where anthropogenic activities may inadvertently expand the eDNA signature beyond the local surveyed sites.

4.2 | Upsides of Citizen Science and eDNA in Port Biodiversity Monitoring

The use of citizen science not only enhances the scale and frequency of monitoring efforts but also enables putting in place processes that can be quickly and easily activated, such as in the case of unpredictable extreme climate events (e.g., storms) (Kvalheim et al. 2024). In the marine environment, citizen science has been used to enhance citizen awareness of biodiversity in the context of marine MPAs, diving spots, and coastline monitoring, such as in the UNESCO Environmental DNA Expeditions, but besides project QUAMPO, not in ports and marinas where it could clearly be a valuable approach, particularly for monitoring biodiversity, detecting invasive species, and engaging the public in environmental conservation efforts (UNESCO 2024). Our findings underlined the growing importance of citizen science and environmental DNA-based monitoring in ports and marinas as an effective tool with an appropriate study design and public engagement, offering a cost-effective means of collecting large amounts of data while also fostering community involvement in marine conservation efforts (Suzuki-Ohno and Kondoh 2023).

These findings demonstrated not only the effectiveness of citizen science but also that data arising from eDNA sampling can lead to a deeper understanding of biodiversity patterns than most of the traditional techniques of biodiversity monitoring (Czachur and Seymour 2021).

4.3 | Higher Fish Biodiversity in October: Seasonal or ECE Effect?

The absence of baseline knowledge of fish biodiversity in the fall in our ports rendered complicated the interpretation of the differences in fish biodiversity observed in our study between the 2 sampling occasions and to clearly disentangle the seasonal effect from the ECE effects. The only other studies that have focused on fish biodiversity in urban marine settings—such as marinas and artificial reefs—and that have explored seasonal patterns in ports include Clynick (2008), who used visual surveys in Sydney Harbor, and Manel et al. (2024) and Macé et al. (2024), who used eDNA in several French Mediterranean ports. These studies generally reported higher total fish diversity in spring and summer compared to fall and winter, in the absence of extreme climatic events (ECEs). However, this seasonal difference was not statistically significant, except in the case of β -diversity reported by Macé et al. (2024). If fish communities in ports “behave” similarly as coastal fish communities, taxonomic richness could be expected to be higher during the reproductive-recruitment season that often peaks in the spring, as found in Deudero et al. (2008) aligning with favorable environmental conditions that support recruitment. As such, the port of Saint-Florent would be the only port to present a response in the fall, consistent with the expected seasonality and did not appear impacted by the ECE contrasting with the responses in the 3 other ports. The port of Saint-Florent, despite being the port under the greatest anthropic pressures (biggest marina and located at 2 river mouths) might host a more resilient ecosystem. Despite a lower taxonomic richness, relative functional and phylogenetic diversity remained high, suggesting that the species present are phylogenetically distant and functionally diverse, which could point toward the presence of few but ecologically and evolutionarily distinct taxa, potentially supporting ecosystem resilience. This interpretation aligns with theoretical frameworks that emphasize the role of ecological complexity and threshold dynamics in ecosystem resilience (Standish et al. 2014). Such functional uniqueness under low species richness may reflect community filtering shaped by multiple co-occurring stressors (Zhang et al. 2024). The inverse relationship between species richness and PD/R, especially in Calvi and L'Île-Rousse, may reflect a tendency for additional species to belong to already represented lineages, resulting in phylogenetic clustering. In contrast, the higher PD/R observed in species-poorer ports like Saint-Florent could indicate the presence of more distantly related taxa. Following the storm in Calvi, the observed decrease in PD/R combined with an increase in FD/R may suggest the recruitment or persistence of species with distinct functional traits but limited phylogenetic novelty—possibly reflecting the influence of opportunistic species typically found in disturbed environments. The biodiversity patterns observed in the fall, in the 3 other ports (Calvi and L'Île-Rousse and in a smaller extent, STARESO), suggested a dynamic interplay between seasonality, port anthropic pressures, and the ECE of August—as

demonstrated in seagrass ecosystems where multiple stressors have reduced resilience (Kendrick et al. 2019)—making these port ecosystems more sensitive to ongoing changes.

Marine ecosystems in temperate regions are increasingly subjected to extreme climate events, such as marine heatwaves (MHWs), which can profoundly impact fish communities and ecosystem services (Smale et al. 2019). The resilience of these communities varies, influenced by factors such as species mobility, habitat complexity, and management practices. A study examining the 2014–2016 MHW in California revealed that while both protected and unprotected rocky reef areas experienced declines in taxonomic and trophic diversity, marine protected areas (MPAs) exhibited a 75% faster recovery in taxonomic diversity compared to adjacent non-protected sites (Ziegler et al. 2023). This reinforces the broader understanding that marine reserves can enhance ecological adaptation to climate stressors (Roberts et al. 2017) even if the size of an MPA is important to play a positive role (Ohayon et al. 2021). Nevertheless, MPAs can enhance the resilience of nearshore fish communities by providing refugia and reducing additional stressors such as fishing pressure, especially in urbanized or semi-urban contexts such as ports where multiple stressors overlap (Putnam et al. 2024). Several other studies have shown that climatic perturbations alter fish communities: Lugo-Carvajal et al. (2022) showed that fires induced by a severe drought led to shifts in Amazonian fish assemblages, Wernberg et al. (2013) highlighted the impact of heat waves on biodiversity patterns in a marine hotspot. Broader analyses indicate that the impacts of MHWs on fish biomass are often unpredictable. A comprehensive study analyzing 248 MHWs across North America and Europe between 1993 and 2019 found that while some events, such as the 2014–2016 Northeast Pacific MHW (“the Blob”), led to significant biomass losses (e.g., a 22% decline in the Gulf of Alaska), others resulted in biomass gains or negligible effects (Fredston et al. 2023). These findings underscore the complexity of fish community responses to extreme climate events and highlight the importance of localized studies to inform conservation and management strategies.

Overall, while certain management interventions, such as the establishment of MPAs, can bolster the resilience of fish communities to ECEs, the variability in responses emphasizes the need for adaptive and context-specific approaches to marine conservation in temperate regions. From an ecological perspective, the role of ports in the coastal ecosystem is not understood. Here, 3 out of the 4 ports experienced an increase in the biodiversity indicators and gained taxonomic, phylogenetic, and functional diversity at a season when taxonomic richness is usually lessened. This could suggest that the port of Calvi, L'Île-Rousse, and to a smaller extent STARESO, with less disturbed habitats, served as a refuge to opportunistic taxa in the aftermath of the ECE that hit Corsica in 2022.

Although each port in this study exhibited distinct combinations of sediment types, hydrological conditions, and anthropogenic pressures, Calvi and L'Île-Rousse were the most similar in terms of seabed characteristics. The port of STARESO was unique among our ports, not being a marina but a natural port with an urbanized part along a drop-off. Surprisingly, it was also

the least taxonomically rich after the port of Saint-Florent and the most consistent with the indicators, with all indicators increasing in the fall.

4.4 | Indicators for Port Biodiversity Monitoring and Possible Contributions to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Port Sustainability Goal and Certification

Our study showed that the integration of citizen science, eDNA analysis, and a multidimensional set of biodiversity indicators yielded robust and consistent results across the four Corsican ports, reinforcing the relevance of this approach for environmental monitoring. The combination of ecological (*R*, *FD*, *PD*) measures, comprehensive ratios (*PD/R*, *FD/R*), and an innovative indicator (*TLmean*) provided a deeper and fairer understanding of biodiversity status within the four Corsican ports than simple ecological measures alone (as for example Villéger et al. (2010) that reported a loss in functional diversity in tropical fish assemblages of an estuary in the Gulf of Mexico, due to a loss of functional specialization, while species richness increased). The ports of Calvi and L'Île-Rousse displayed the highest values for raw indicators (*R*, *PD*, *FD*), but their relative indicators (*PD/R* and *FD/R*) were lower than expected given their richness. This highlights that high taxonomic richness does not necessarily imply high functional or phylogenetic distinctiveness, stressing the need to standardize metrics to avoid biased conclusions based solely on raw values. By contrast, Saint-Florent, despite its low taxonomic richness, exhibited the highest *PD/R* and a high *FD/R*, with only 16 functional entities. This suggests that species in Saint-Florent, though few, were phylogenetically distant and functionally diverse, offering ecologically meaningful insights into community structure under anthropogenic pressure. Seasonal contrasts further reinforced the non-redundancy of *FD* and *PD*. In three of the four ports (Calvi, L'Île-Rousse, and Saint-Florent), relative *FD* and *PD* varied in opposite directions between spring and fall, confirming that these indicators respond differently to seasonal drivers or stressors, as also suggested by (Marques et al. 2021) and supported by trait-based filtering observed under anthropogenic homogenization (Moi et al. 2023). Our results challenge the assumption that *PD* is a reliable surrogate for *FD*, showing that each indicator—raw or relative, taxonomic, phylogenetic, or functional—captures distinct facets of biodiversity. Relying on a single type would obscure important aspects of ecosystem structure, whereas their combination offers a fairer and more actionable understanding of biodiversity responses to anthropization.

The inclusion of relevant metrics and indicators in the AFNOR certification “Clean Ports Active in Biodiversity” is critical to ensuring that ports can quantitatively track their biodiversity performance and demonstrate meaningful progress toward sustainability goals. The “Clean Ports Active in Biodiversity” certification is an extension of the “Clean Ports” initiative, designed to encourage port managers to implement sustainable biodiversity practices in addition to environmental cleanliness. Launched in 2018 with the support of AFNOR and various regional and environmental bodies, this certification focuses on enhancing biodiversity in and around ports. It is available only to ports already certified under the “Clean Ports” label and aims

to align port operations with biodiversity conservation. The certification evaluates and verifies that the ports actively engage in actions that promote biodiversity, considering terrestrial and marine habitats. Since 2024, the certification has been integrated into the global ISO 18725 standard, which sets guidelines for “clean ports” in terms of biodiversity actions and environmental standards. In this context, embedding relevant, scientifically backed biodiversity indicators within the “Clean Ports Active in Biodiversity” certification framework is essential for guiding ports toward sustainable operations. These metrics ensure that biodiversity goals are tangible, trackable, and integrable into port management practices, helping foster an active role in biodiversity conservation. As such, developing well-defined, measurable indicators offers several key advantages:

1. **Objective Measurement:** Metrics allow for clear evaluation of port activities on biodiversity, offering quantifiable insights into areas like species richness, habitat quality, and water quality. Indicators such as the Sørensen or Jaccard similarity index for species composition or the Phylogenetic Diversity (*PD*) index provide scientific benchmarks for monitoring biodiversity trends over time.
2. **Tracking Impact and Progress:** By using biological indicators such as the presence of key species, functional diversity, or population trends, ports can assess whether their conservation actions are improving or degrading local ecosystems. Metrics tied to ecosystem services, such as pollution reduction or habitat restoration, are essential to evaluate the overall environmental footprint of the port's operations.
3. **Standardization and Comparability:** The adoption of specific indicators enables comparability across different ports, creating a unified approach to biodiversity management. This standardization can be instrumental in benchmarking performance against international best practices and promoting transparency in port management strategies.
4. **Informed Decision-Making:** Indicators provide ports with data-driven insights, enabling more effective decision-making. For example, tracking species vulnerability indices or monitoring changes in taxonomic richness can guide adaptive management, helping ports respond to ecological changes more swiftly.
5. **Regulatory and Certification Compliance:** Measurable indicators align port operations with legislative requirements and certification criteria. Having established metrics ensures compliance with environmental regulations and helps ports meet the standards necessary for certification under AFNOR.

Given the current lack of systematic biodiversity baselines in port ecosystems—particularly in urban coastal areas—our results may help establish reference conditions under the MSFD. Specifically, the multi-indicator approach used in this study, combining taxonomic, phylogenetic, functional, and trophic data derived from eDNA, provides a promising framework to inform D1 indicators. These findings could support the development of baseline datasets essential for evaluating Good Environmental Status (GES), especially in anthropogenically modified and under-monitored habitats such as ports. This

multi-approach indicator is also particularly relevant for indicators that are difficult to interpret in isolation, such as *TLmean* in line with current guidance on the use of trophic indicators under the MSFD Descriptor 4 (MSFD D4), which emphasizes caution in their application. As highlighted by the European Commission (2017), the French national MSFD assessment (Ministère de la Transition écologique and Ifremer 2018), and the final D4 evaluation report (OFB et al. 2018), trophic indicators are highly context-dependent and must be interpreted within a broader ecological and methodological framework to avoid misrepresentation. Given the resolution of eDNA data and the current lack of standardized trophic assignments for many species detected, we opted not to emphasize trophic indicators in isolation but rather to integrate them qualitatively within a suite of complementary indicators. Future work, ideally supported by more detailed ecological and contextual data and refined trophic classifications, could allow for more robust and meaningful analyses of food web dynamics.

Each of the four studied ports exhibited distinct biodiversity profiles. Calvi and L'Île-Rousse were the most similar and often showed the highest values for raw indicators. However, they did not always score highest for relative metrics, underlining the importance of contextualized indicators. Notably, Saint-Florent emerged as an outlier across all biodiversity dimensions, demonstrating that effective biodiversity practices cannot be generalized and must be adapted to each port's specific context. Finally, the results from STARESO—a site with minimal anthropogenic pressure and closest to a pristine coastal habitat—were surprising. Despite its low level of disturbance, its biodiversity levels were lower across most indicators compared to more anthropized ports like Calvi and L'Île-Rousse, revealing the complex relationship between human activity and biodiversity in port environments.

5 | Conclusion

The scarcity in literature on fish diversity in urban marine environment such as ports underscores the novelty and importance of our study in contributing to an underrepresented and increasingly urgent research area given current climate projections (IPCC 2023) and highlights the need for more targeted investigations in urban marine contexts (Madon et al. 2023). Our study used advanced biodiversity indicators, such as the PD/R and FD/R ratios, which contextualized taxonomic richness within evolutionary and functional frameworks. These metrics extended beyond traditional species counts, highlighting ecosystem-level responses to intersecting climatic and anthropogenic pressures and could contribute to the development of essential biodiversity variables (EBVs). Furthermore, our results revealed that biodiversity within ports in Corsica is substantial. Corsican ports appeared to harbor at least 20% of the teleost biodiversity in Corsica and 11% of the Mediterranean teleost biodiversity (Froese and Pauly 2010). Additional research is needed to estimate relative phylogenetic diversity, enabling an assessment of the proportion of total phylogenetic diversity, known for the Mediterranean and Corsica, that is present in ports. Such knowledge would allow a more comprehensive evaluation of the biodiversity supported by these urbanized ecosystems and is even more necessary than Corsica appeared as a refugia for sharks

and rays but also threatened fishes in the latest study using eDNA in this region (Pichot et al. 2024). These findings compared to the results in the Calvi area in Dalongeville et al. (2022) seemed to corroborate those of Manel et al. (2024) in that port taxonomic richness appeared similar than nearby protected areas and question the belief that urbanized ecosystems host less species and functional diversity in the marine environment (Moi et al. 2023). From our results, the role of ports in the coastal ecosystem appeared context-dependent. This is particularly relevant in the face of climate-driven biodiversity reshuffling and ecosystem instability (Kendrick et al. 2019). While they primarily contribute to habitat degradation through pollution, habitat destruction, and introduction of invasive species, they can also serve as opportunistic habitats and potentially act as refuge under extreme climate events (Fredston et al. 2023; Wernberg et al. 2013; Ziegler et al. 2023). This dual nature emphasizes the need for more research and targeted conservation efforts to better understand and mitigate the ecological impacts of ports while exploring their potential as habitats in highly urbanized coastal areas. Understanding port characteristics and intrinsic pressures on biodiversity can help guide conservation and management efforts in ports. Through the implementation of “green ports” initiative or the AFNOR certification “Clean Ports Active in Biodiversity”, the mitigation of anthropic pressures by promoting sustainable practices, restoring in and surrounding habitats, creating and reducing pollution can transform ports into areas that contribute positively to local biodiversity (Putnam et al. 2024). Finally, the integration of cutting-edge metabarcoding technology based on eDNA with the community-driven power of citizen science not only enhances local biodiversity monitoring but also represents a scalable model for global conservation efforts. Such frameworks have already demonstrated their effectiveness and community engagement in global programmes like the UNESCO Environmental DNA Expeditions (UNESCO 2024).

As climate change accelerates, such collaborative approaches coupled with open and FAIR approaches to share the data will become increasingly critical in safeguarding vulnerable ecosystems from the mounting threats of extreme climate events (David et al. 2023; Madon et al. 2024; Wilkinson et al. 2016). In the face of increasingly frequent ECEs, such as hurricanes, heatwaves, floods, and derechos, which are now recognized as critical drivers of biodiversity collapse at a global scale (Smale et al. 2019), integrating disaster preparedness into biodiversity conservation strategies has become critically important. ECEs can lead to abrupt and often severe disruptions in species composition, population dynamics, and ecosystem functioning, particularly in already stressed environments such as urbanized coastal zones. Effective conservation strategies must therefore anticipate these events by incorporating adaptive management plans, early warning systems, and rapid biodiversity assessment tools such as eDNA and metabarcoding. This proactive approach allows for timely evaluation of biodiversity baselines and post-disturbance shifts, enabling conservation practitioners to identify vulnerable species, prioritize habitat restoration, and monitor cascading effects across trophic and functional levels, as suggested in recent ECE impact reviews (Fredston et al. 2023; Wernberg et al. 2013). Ultimately, aligning biodiversity conservation with disaster preparedness not only safeguards ecological integrity during crises but also strengthens long-term

sustainability and recovery capacity in the face of climate uncertainty. Such a role is particularly relevant in the context of intensifying extreme climate events (ECEs), which can drive both ecological collapse and resilience depending on local context (Fredston et al. 2023; Wernberg et al. 2013; Ziegler et al. 2023; Kendrick et al. 2019) and anticipating future risks through early warning systems and rapid biodiversity assessment methods (Putnam et al. 2024).

Author Contributions

The conception or design of the study: B.M. and H.T. The acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of the data: all authors. Writing of the manuscript: all authors.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to all individuals who supported, facilitated, and participated in the data collection process. Their contributions and support were invaluable to the success of this research: students and teachers from the Albert Camus Primary School in L'Île-Rousse and the Primary School in Belgodère; Blaise Dary from the L'Île-Rousse town hall & Jean-Stéphane Allegrini-Simonetti from the Corsica Chamber of Commerce and Industry; Laurent Guerini from the Calvi town hall; Directors of Corsican ports: Martine Jolibois & Jean-Christophe Antonelli (Île Rousse), Philippe Gabrielli & Jean-Christophe Albertini (Calvi), David Donnini (Saint-Florent); Colleagues from the EMFF QUAMPO project: Justine Castec & Clémence Epinoux; Ms. Séverine Adobati from the Corsica Maritime and Coastal Directorate. The authors are deeply appreciative of the time, effort, and expertise contributed by all these individuals, which greatly enhanced the quality and scope of this research. The authors also thank David Mouillot for providing the sequence reference database, which improved the accuracy of species identification in our analysis. This study was carried out in the framework of the EMFF QUAMPO project (grant no. PFEA800219DM0940001), Horizon Europe Project DANUBIUS-IP (grant no. 101079778) and SAFARI (grant no. 101147432). This research was also funded by the "Agence de l'eau Rhône Méditerranée Corse" and the "Collectivité de Corse" (CdC), as part of the STARECAPMED project research.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data are openly available on GBIF: <https://www.gbif-uat.org/dataset/542de543-5e19-4d6d-835b-8531b7d90a26>. Codes are available at the following github: https://github.com/HaderleRachel/Biodiv_Port_Corsica_eDNA.git.

References

Aglieri, G., F. Quattrocchi, S. Mariani, et al. 2023. "Fish eDNA Detections in Ports Mirror Fishing Fleet Activities and Highlight the Spread of Non-Indigenous Species in the Mediterranean Sea." *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 189: 114792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.114792>.

Baird, D. J., and M. Hajibabaei. 2012. "Biomonitoring 2.0: A New Paradigm in Ecosystem Assessment Made Possible by Next-Generation DNA Sequencing." *Molecular Ecology* 21, no. 8: 2039–2044. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2012.05519.x>.

Baselga, A. 2012. "The Relationship Between Species Replacement, Dissimilarity Derived From Nestedness, and Nestedness." *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 21, no. 12: 1223–1232. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2011.00756.x>.

Biggs, J., N. Ewald, A. Valentini, et al. 2015. "Using eDNA to Develop a National Citizen Science-Based Monitoring Programme for the Great Crested Newt (*Triturus cristatus*)." *Biological Conservation* 183, no. 1: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.029>.

Boettiger, C., D. T. Lang, and P. C. Wainwright. 2012. "Rfishbase: Exploring, Manipulating and Visualizing FishBase Data From R." *Journal of Fish Biology* 81, no. 6: 2030–2039. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8649.2012.03464.x>.

Bonney, R., C. B. Cooper, J. Dickinson, et al. 2009. "Citizen Science: A Developing Tool for Expanding Science Knowledge and Scientific Literacy." *BioScience* 59, no. 11: 977–984. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2009.59.11.9>.

Boyer, F., C. Mercier, A. Bonin, Y. Le Bras, P. Taberlet, and E. Coissac. 2016. "OBITOOLS: A UNIX-Inspired Software Package for DNA Metabarcoding." *Molecular Ecology Resources* 16: 176–182.

Charvoz, L., L. Apothéoz-Perret-Gentil, J. Pawlowski, et al. 2021. "Monitoring Newt Communities in Urban Area Using eDNA Metabarcoding." *PeerJ* 9, no. 1: e12357. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.12357>.

Clynick, B. G. 2008. "Characteristics of an Urban Fish Assemblage: Distribution of Fish Associated With Coastal Marinas." *Marine Environmental Research* 65, no. 1: 18–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2007.07.005>.

Coché, L., E. Arnaud, L. Bouveret, et al. 2021. "Kakila Database: Towards a FAIR Community-Approved Database of Cetacean Presence in the Waters of the Guadeloupe Archipelago, Based on Citizen Science." *Biodiversity Data Journal* 9, no. 1: e69022. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.9.e69022>.

Cohn, J. P. 2008. "Citizen Science: Can Volunteers Do Real Research?" *BioScience* 58, no. 3: 192–197. <https://doi.org/10.1641/B580303>.

Couvet, D., F. Jiguet, R. Julliard, H. Levrel, and A. Teysseire. 2008. "Enhancing Citizen Contributions to Biodiversity Science and Public Policy." *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews* 33, no. 1: 95–103. <https://doi.org/10.1179/030801808X260031>.

Czachur, M. V., and M. Seymour. 2021. "Novel Insights Into Marine Fish Biodiversity Across a Pronounced Environmental Gradient Using Replicated Environmental DNA Analyses." *Environmental DNA* 4: 181–190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.238>.

Dalongeville, A., E. Boulanger, V. Marques, et al. 2022. "Benchmarking Eleven Biodiversity Indicators Based on Environmental DNA Surveys: More Diverse Functional Traits and Evolutionary Lineages Inside Marine Reserves." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 59: 2803–2813. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14276>.

David, R., A. Rybina, J.-M. Burel, et al. 2023. "Be Sustainable: EOSC-Life Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Principles in Life Science Data Handling." *EMBO Journal* 42, no. 23: e115008. <https://doi.org/10.15252/emj.2023115008>.

de Sherbinin, A., A. Bowser, T.-R. Chuang, et al. 2021. "The Critical Importance of Citizen Science Data." *Frontiers in Climate* 3, no. 1: 650760. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.650760>.

Deudero, S., G. Morey, A. Frau, J. Moranta, and I. Moreno. 2008. "Temporal Trends of Littoral Fishes at Deep Posidonia Oceanica Seagrass Meadows in a Temperate Coastal Zone." *Journal of Marine Systems* 70, no. 1–2: 182–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2007.05.001>.

Dray, S., R. Pélissier, P. Couteron, et al. 2012. "Community Ecology in the Age of Multivariate Multiscale Spatial Analysis." *Ecological Monographs* 82, no. 3: 257–275. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-1183.1>.

European Commission. 2017. "Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 Laying Down Criteria and Methodological Standards on Good Environmental Status of Marine Waters and Specifications and Standardised Methods for Monitoring and Assessment." *Official*

- Journal of the European Union* 125: 43–74. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017D0848>.
- Faith, D. P. 1992. “Conservation Evaluation and Phylogenetic Diversity.” *Biological Conservation* 61, no. 1: 1–10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(92\)91201-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(92)91201-3).
- Fraisl, D., G. Hager, B. Bedessem, et al. 2022. “Citizen Science in Environmental and Ecological Sciences.” *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 2, no. 1: 64. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00144-4>.
- Fredston, A. L., W. W. L. Cheung, T. L. Frölicher, et al. 2023. “Marine Heatwaves Are Not a Dominant Driver of Change in Demersal Fishes.” *Nature* 621: 324–329. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06449-y>.
- Froese, R., and D. Pauly. 2010. “FishBase. World Wide Web Electronic Publication.” www.fishbase.org.
- Gower, J. C., and M. J. Warrens. 2017. *Similarity, Dissimilarity, and Distance Measures*, 1–11. Wiley StatsRef: Statistics Reference Online. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118445112.stat02470.pub2>.
- Haderlé, R., L. Bouveret, J. Chazal, et al. 2024. “eDNA-Based Survey of the Marine Vertebrate Biodiversity Off the West Coast of Guadeloupe (French West Indies).” *Biodiversity Data Journal* 12: e125348. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.12.e125348>.
- Haklay, M., D. Fraisl, B. Greshake Tzovaras, et al. 2021. “What Is Citizen Science? The Challenges of Definition.” In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, et al., 13–33. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_2.
- IPCC. 2023. *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report Summary for Policymakers*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Report.
- Kassambara, A., and F. Mundt. 2017. “Package ‘Factoextra’ Extract and Visualize the Results of Multivariate Data Analyses, 76, 10-18637.”
- Kembel, S. W., P. D. Cowan, M. R. Helmus, et al. 2010. “Picante: R Tools for Integrating Phylogenies and Ecology.” *Bioinformatics* 26, no. 11: 1463–1464. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq166>.
- Kendrick, G. A., R. J. Nowicki, Y. S. Olsen, et al. 2019. “A Systematic Review of How Multiple Stressors From an Extreme Event Drove Ecosystem-Wide Loss of Resilience in an Iconic Seagrass Community.” *Frontiers in Marine Science* 6: 455. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00455>.
- Kenworthy, J. M., G. Rolland, S. Samadi, and C. Lejeusne. 2018. “Local Variation Within Marinas: Effects of Pollutants and Implications for Invasive Species.” *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 133, no. 1: 96–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.05.001>.
- Knudsen, S. W., C. Rahbek, J. Koch Sheard, et al. 2023. “Detection of Environmental DNA From Amphibians in Northern Europe Applied in Citizen Science.” *Environmental DNA* 5: 1429–1448. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.462>.
- Kvalheim, L., E. Stensrud, A. Eiler, H. Knutsen, and O. Hyvärinen. 2024. “Integration of Citizen Science and eDNA Reveals Novel Ecological Insights for Marine Fish Conservation.” *Environmental DNA* 6: e584. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.584>.
- Lehtiniemi, M., O. Outinen, and R. Puntilla-Dodd. 2020. “Citizen Science Provides Added Value in the Monitoring for Coastal Non-Indigenous Species.” *Journal of Environmental Management* 267, no. 1: 110608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110608>.
- Li, D. 2023. “Rtrees: An R Package to Assemble Phylogenetic Trees From Megatrees.” *Ecography* 2023, no. 7: e06643. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.06643>.
- Lugo-Carvajal, A., M. Holmgren, J. Zuanon, and P. van der Sleen. 2022. “Fish on Fire: Shifts in Amazonian Fish Communities After Floodplain Forest Fires.” *Journal of Applied Ecology* 60: 1637–1646. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14434>.
- Luzar, J. B., K. M. Silvius, H. Overman, S. T. Giery, J. M. Read, and J. M. V. Fragoso. 2011. “Large-Scale Environmental Monitoring by Indigenous Peoples.” *BioScience* 61, no. 10: 771–781. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2011.61.10.7>.
- MacConaill, L. E., R. T. Burns, A. Nag, et al. 2018. “Unique, Dual-Indexed Sequencing Adapters With UMIs Effectively Eliminate Index Cross-Talk and Significantly Improve Sensitivity of Massively Parallel Sequencing.” *BMC Genomics* 19, no. 1: 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S12864-017-4428-5>.
- Macé, B., D. Mouillot, A. Dalongeville, et al. 2024. “The Tree of Life eDNA Metabarcoding Reveals a Similar Taxonomic Richness but Dissimilar Evolutionary Lineages Between Seaports and Marine Reserves.” *Molecular Ecology* 33: e17373. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.17373>.
- Madon, B., R. David, C. Epinoux, et al. 2024. “Chapter 4: Lessons Learned and Best Practices in Developing an Information System for Interdisciplinary, Heterogeneous, Multidimensional Environmental Data: The WIBE (Water Interdisciplinary Biology and Ecology) Information System.” In *Best Practices in Port Environmental Data Management. The Case Study of the WIBE Information System*, edited by F. Muttin and H. Thomas. ISTE Ltd. <https://www.istegroup.com/en/produit/best-practices-in-port-environmental-data-management/>.
- Madon, B., R. David, A. Torralba, et al. 2023. “A Review of Biodiversity Research in Ports: Let’s Not Overlook Everyday Nature!” *Ocean and Coastal Management* 242, no. 1: 106623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106623>.
- Madon, B., D. Le Guyader, J.-L. Jung, et al. 2022. “Pairing AIS Data and Underwater Topography to Assess Maritime Traffic Pressures on Cetaceans: Case Study in the Guadeloupean Waters of the Agoa Sanctuary.” *Marine Policy* 143: 105160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105160>.
- Manel, S., L. Mathon, D. Mouillot, et al. 2024. “Benchmarking Fish Biodiversity of Seaports With eDNA and Nearby Marine Reserves.” *Conservation Letters* 17: e13001. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.13001>.
- Marques, V., P. Castagné, A. P. Fernández, et al. 2021. “Use of Environmental DNA in Assessment of Fish Functional and Phylogenetic Diversity.” *Conservation Biology* 35: 1944–1956. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13802>.
- Ministère de la Transition écologique, Ifremer. 2018. “Mise à jour 2018 de l’évaluation initiale, de la définition du bon état écologique et des programmes de surveillance au titre de la directive cadre stratégie pour le milieu marin (DCSMM).” <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/directive-cadre-strategie-pour-milieu-marin-dcsmm>.
- Moi, D. A., M. Barrios, G. Tesitore, et al. 2023. “Human Land-Uses Homogenize Stream Assemblages and Reduce Animal Biomass Production.” *Journal of Animal Ecology* 92: 1176–1189. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13924>.
- Mouillot, D., N. Loiseau, M. Grenié, et al. 2021. “The Dimensionality and Structure of Species Trait Spaces.” *Ecology Letters* 24, no. 9: 1988–2009. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13778>.
- OFB, Ifremer, and AFB. 2018. *Descripteur 4: Réseaux Trophiques—Rapport d’évaluation finale pour la DCSMM*. Milieu Marin France. https://dcsmm.milieu marin france.fr/content/download/4755/file/Rapport_final_D4.pdf.
- Ohayon, S., I. Granot, and J. Belmaker. 2021. “A Meta-Analysis Reveals Edge Effects Within Marine Protected Areas.” *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 5: 1301–1308. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01502-3>.
- Pal, A., and P. Mukhopadhyay. 2022. “Fetching Automatic Authority Data in ILS From Wikidata via OpenRefine.” *SRELS Journal of Information Management* 59, no. 6: 353–362. <https://doi.org/10.17821/srels/2022/v59i6/170677>.
- Pichot, F., D. Mouillot, J.-B. Juhel, et al. 2024. “Mediterranean Islands as Refugia for Elasmobranch and Threatened Fishes.” *Diversity and Distributions* 31: e13937. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13937>.

- Polanco Fernández, A., V. Marques, F. Fopp, et al. 2021. “Comparing Environmental DNA Metabarcoding and Underwater Visual Census to Monitor Tropical Reef Fishes.” *Environmental DNA* 3, no. 1: 142–156. <https://doi.org/10.1002/EDN3.140>.
- Pucik, T. 2022. “The Derecho and Hailstorms of 18 August 2022. European Severe Storms Laboratory.” ESSL.org.
- Putnam, A. B., S. C. Endyke, A. R. Jones, et al. 2024. “Historical Insights, Current Challenges: Tracking Marine Biodiversity in an Urban Harbor Ecosystem in the Face of Climate Change.” *Marine Biodiversity* 54: 78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-024-01462-4>.
- Roberts, C. M., B. C. O’Leary, D. J. McCauley, et al. 2017. “Marine Reserves Can Mitigate and Promote Adaptation to Climate Change.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 114, no. 24: 6167–6175. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1701262114>.
- Sandahl, A., and A. P. Tøttrup. 2020. “Marine Citizen Science: Recent Developments and Future Recommendations.” *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* 5: 24. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.270>.
- Schnell, I. B., K. Bohmann, and M. T. P. Gilbert. 2015. “Tag Jumps Illuminated—Reducing Sequence-To-Sample Misidentifications in Metabarcoding Studies.” *Molecular Ecology Resources* 15, no. 6: 1289–1303. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12402>.
- Smale, D. A., T. Wernberg, E. C. J. Oliver, et al. 2019. “Marine Heatwaves Threaten Global Biodiversity and the Provision of Ecosystem Services.” *Nature Climate Change* 9: 306–312. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-019-0412-1>.
- Standish, R. J., R. J. Hobbs, M. M. Mayfield, et al. 2014. “Resilience in Ecology: Abstraction, Distraction, or Where the Action Is?” *Biological Conservation* 177: 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.06.008>.
- Suzuki-Ohno, Y., and M. Kondoh. 2023. “Evaluation of Community Science Monitoring With Environmental DNA for Marine Fish Species: ‘Fish Survey Project Using Environmental DNA.’” *Environmental DNA* 5: 613–623. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.425>.
- UNESCO, S. Suominen, P. Provoost, et al. 2024. *Engaging Communities to Safeguard Ocean Life: UNESCO Environmental DNA Expeditions*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.58337/CBXU3518>.
- Valentini, A., F. Pompanon, and P. Taberlet. 2009. “DNA Barcoding for Ecologists.” *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 24, no. 2: 110–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2008.09.011>.
- Valentini, A., P. Taberlet, C. Miaud, et al. 2016. “Next-Generation Monitoring of Aquatic Biodiversity Using Environmental DNA Metabarcoding.” *Molecular Ecology* 25: 929–942. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13428>.
- Villéger, S., J. Ramos Miranda, D. Flores Hernández, J. R. Miranda, D. F. Hernández, and D. Mouillot. 2010. “Contrasting Changes in Taxonomic vs. Functional Diversity of Tropical Fish Communities After Habitat Degradation.” *Ecological Applications* 20, no. 6: 1512–1522. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-1310.1>.
- Wernberg, T., D. Smale, F. Tuya, et al. 2013. “An Extreme Climatic Event Alters Marine Ecosystem Structure in a Global Biodiversity Hotspot.” *Nature Climate Change* 3, no. 1: 78–82. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1627>.
- Wilkinson, M. D., M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3: 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- Zhang, S., A. Zhan, J. Zhao, and M. Yao. 2024. “Metropolitan Pressures: Significant Biodiversity Declines and Strong Filtering of Functional Traits in Fish Assemblages.” *Science of the Total Environment* 944: 173885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173885>.
- Ziegler, S. L., J. M. Johnson, R. O. Brooks, et al. 2023. “Marine Protected Areas, Marine Heatwaves, and the Resilience of Nearshore Fish Communities.” *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 1: 1405. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28507-1>.

Appendix 1

Maps of the nature of the seabed in and around the four sampled ports and sampling sites within each port (green stars): Saint-Florent, L'Île-Rousse, Calvi and STARES0.

NATURE OF THE SEABED IN THE BAY OF CALVI

Nature of the seabed

- Coralligenous
- Cymodocea meadow
- Soft substrates (sands)
- Pebbles
- Posidonia meadow
- Hard substrates (rocks)
- Artificial substrates

0 250 500 m

Data sources : STARESO (Location of ports) ; IGN, 2017 (BDORTHO) ; SHOM/IGN, 2013 (coastline histolit v2) ; Seaviews, 2018 (nature of the seabed) ; SHOM, 2018 (Litto3D MNT bathymétrie) ; Emodnet Digital Bathymétrie, DTM 2020

Map projection : WGS 84 / EPSG 4326

Realisation : STARESO

Appendix 2

Average rarefaction (saturation) curves for each sample based on 100 iterations. Curves show the cumulative number of distinct taxa detected as a function of sequencing depth.

Average Saturation Curves by Sample (100 Iterations)

Appendix 3

Biodiversity indicator values in the Spring (“_Spring”) and in the fall after the storm (“_PS”) in the 4 Corsican ports in 2022.

	R	PD	PD/R	FD	FD/R	TLmean (se)	Vulner	RedList
Calvi_Spring	28	1943	72	24	0.85	3.18 (0.4)	34	0
Calvi_PS	43	2773	68	39	0.9	3.38 (0.5)	38	2
L'Île-Rousse_Spring	27	1655	64	24	0.89	3.33 (0.5)	42	0
L'Île-Rousse_PS	44	3022	70	36	0.82	3.36 (0.53)	37	0
Saint-Florent_Spring	25	1777	71	22	0.88	3.17 (0.52)	42	0
Saint-Florent_PS	18	1425	79	16	0.89	3.05 (0.42)	43	0
STARESO_Spring	23	1493	65	18	0.78	3.23 (0.37)	34	0
STARESO_PS	34	2186	64	30	0.88	3.22 (0.46)	35	1